

Improving the accuracy of mobile manipulators by means of force sensors

Giovanni Boschetti

Department of Industrial Engineering
 University of Padova
 Padova, Italy
 giovanni.boschetti@unipd.it

Riccardo Minto

Department of Industrial Engineering
 University of Padova
 Padova, Italy
 riccardo.minto@unipd.it

Michele Tonan

Department of Industrial Engineering
 University of Padova
 Padova, Italy
 michele.tonan@phd.unipd.it

Abstract—For a mobile manipulator to be effective, it must ensure sufficient accuracy to carry out the task. To improve the accuracy of a mobile manipulator, this paper presents a tip localization strategy which takes advantage of the force sensors built into the manipulator. Experimental tests compared the approach with traditional strategies implemented in the system.

Index Terms—mobile robot, tip localization, force sensors

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, mobile robots have become increasingly common in satisfying the requirements of modern industrial plants, which feature a network of interconnected workstations. To take further advantage of these robots, it is common for mobile platforms to carry manipulators used for pick and place tasks, or even minor assembly tasks [1]. Hence, it is fundamental to precisely know the position of the robot end-effector to complete the assigned task [2]. The most common technique for localization is achieved by means of vision sensors [3], based on perception cameras or laser scanner sensors mounted on the mobile platform, or light detection and ranging (LIDAR) scanners, to compensate for its imprecision. However, vision-based approaches may fail in an unstructured environment [4], since there may not be objects to be used as landmarks.

This work aims to present an approach to improve the accuracy of a mobile manipulator based on force sensors used to localize precision points in the workspace. This is especially convenient when considering that, for safety issues, the majority of commercial mobile platforms carry collaborative robots, which feature built-in force sensors and which may be used as measuring tools [5].

II. TIP LOCALIZATION APPROACH

The proposed approach starts with an initial movement of the mobile platform towards the target destination, which may be carried out with or without any localization approach. When the platform arrives and stops at the target destination, which is placed at a sufficient distance (about 450 mm in the proposed scenario) from the working area as seen in Figure 1, the controller starts the localization procedure, which begins with an evaluation of the angular error, followed by an evaluation in the x -direction and in the y -direction.

To evaluate the angular error, the manipulator moves the tool tip along the x -axis of the arm reference frame, touching the working area in two points (points 1 and 2 in Figure 1), which are placed at a known distance. When the force sensors measure an impact, the tool tip coordinates in the arm frame are memorized, and the angular error in the base frame is evaluated as follows

$$e_{\theta} = \text{atan} \left(\frac{x_2 - x_1}{y_2 - y_1} \right) \quad (1)$$

where the ratio is determined by the rotation of 90° around the z -axis between the base frame and the arm frame. Following the evaluation of e_{θ} , the controller adjusts the mobile frame before evaluating the remaining errors.

Fig. 1. System layout reference frames and measurement points for the localization process.

For the evaluation of the x -axis error, e_x , the manipulator, whose reference frame axes are now properly aligned with the ones of the working area, moves the tool tip to sweep a portion of the working area till it collides with a reference cylinder (the black circle in Figure 2), identifying point 3. Hence, it is possible to evaluate e_x as follows:

$$e_x = x_T - (y_3 \pm (w/2 + r)) \quad (2)$$

where x_T is the theoretical value of the x -coordinate of the mobile platform in the base reference frame, y_3 is the y -axis coordinate of point 3 in the arm reference frame, w is the width of the tool tip, and r is the radius of the cylinder. The \pm symbol depends on the direction of motion during the collision. Lastly, the error e_y along the y -axis of the base reference frame is evaluated by moving the end-effector along the x -axis of the manipulator till it collides with the cylinder at point 4 (green

Fig. 2. Trajectories for the evaluation of the error e_x (blue) and of the error e_y (green).

trajectory in Figure 2). This is possible by means of the two previous evaluations. Hence, e_y is evaluated as follows:

$$e_y = y_T - (x_4 - L) \quad (3)$$

where y_T is the theoretical value of the y -coordinate of the platform in the base reference frame, x_4 is the value of the x -coordinate of point 4 in the arm reference frame, and L is the length of the tool tip.

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The approach was tested on the KUKA KMR iiwa platform, a mobile robot composed of an omnidirectional mobile platform and a 7-DOF collaborative robot equipped with torque sensors. The robot mounts a SCHUNK Co-act gripper and a properly design tool to touch the reference points, as seen in Figure 3. In this work, we will compare the Cartesian position

Fig. 3. Tool adopted in the experimental setup; notice the customized end-effector (gray) which features the tip for the localization process.

and angular errors achieved with a basic approach based on the odometry of the robot, with a lidar-based SLAM, and with the proposed method. A comparison of the angular error e_θ in Figure 4 shows that the proposed approach (green) fares much better than the odometry-based approach (orange, with a mean e_θ equal to 4.88°) and better than the lidar-based approach (blue, with a mean e_θ equal to 0.84°), with a mean error of 0.43° .

Since the velocity of the end-effector may affect the precision of the approach during the evaluation of e_x and e_y , the approach was tested for different values of the Cartesian velocity, i.e., for an arm speed of 15, 25, and 35 mm/s, as seen in Figure 5.

While the mean values of e_x for the odometry-based approach and for the lidar-based one are equal to 58.14 and 3.08

Fig. 4. Comparison of the different approaches: angular error

Fig. 5. Comparison of the position error for different values of the manipulator velocity.

mm, respectively, the value achieved by the proposed approach is equal to 1.714 mm for a speed value of 15 mm/s and equal to 0.86 mm for a speed value of 25 mm/s, respectively. The high value achieved for 35 mm/s (equal to 9.928 mm) is due to the impact force measured, which exceeds the force limit value too quickly for the sensors; different sensors may improve the velocity value. A similar behaviour is seen when comparing e_y , which is equal to 107.55 mm for the odometry-based approach and equal to 4.61 mm for the lidar-based one: the proposed approach ranges between 0.98 mm and 0.58 mm. Given the high value of e_x 35 mm/s, it is not possible to reliably measure e_y with the proposed approach.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents a localization strategy based on force-sensing to improve the accuracy of mobile robots. Experimental tests were carried out to compare the proposed strategy with traditional approaches, showing the advantages of the strategy in reducing the localization error.

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